

Due Economy is Based on Authenticity? Authentic Leader's Personality and Employees' Voice Behaviour

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Abstract *The study examines the impact of authentic leader's personality on employee voice behavior through a quantitative study. The results, from a sample of 200 subordinate-supervisor dyads from a healthcare organization in Pakistan, provide evidence of a positive relationship for leader authentic personality with direct reports' ratings of the leaders' authentic leadership. In addition, authentic leadership was found to influence subordinates' voice behavior, as rated by subordinates' immediate supervisors; notably, this relationship was partially mediated by the subordinates' perceptions of OBSE. Furthermore, leader authentic personality was indirectly related to subordinates' voice behaviour through the mediating influence of authentic leadership and, in turn, subordinates' perceptions of Organization-based self-esteem. The findings of this study will make management understand the linkage of an authentic leader's personality and employee voice behavior.*

Key Words:

Leader Authentic Personality, Authentic Leadership, Organization-Based Self-Esteem (OBSE), Employee Voice Behavior

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Introduction

Authentic leadership, or the extent to which leaders remain “true to themselves”, refers to “a pattern of leader behaviour that draws upon and promotes both positive psychological capacities and a positive ethical climate to foster greater self-awareness, an internalized moral perspective, balanced processing of information, and relational transparency on the part of leaders working with followers, fostering positive self-development” (Walumbwa, Avolio, Gardner, Wernsing, & Peterson, 2008, p. 94).

The aforementioned research has elucidated the effectiveness of authentic leadership. Nevertheless, scholars have devoted little attention to clarifying the process of authentic leadership development (i.e., from its antecedents to its outcomes). Gardner, Cogliser, Davis, and Dickens (2011) noted that many major questions pertaining to the antecedents and consequences of authentic leadership have not been answered. For the study of authentic leadership to progress, researchers must systematically examine who engages in authentic leadership and why and how authentic leadership matters. Thus, consistent with the suggestion of Gardner et al. (2011) regarding the expansion of the authentic leadership

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nomological network, the objective of the current study is to clarify the theoretical understanding of the antecedents and consequences of authentic leadership.

To fill the void in the authentic leadership literature, it explores the influence of an individual difference variable that may affect the perception of authentic leadership. Specifically, it identifies dispositional authenticity as a critical personal characteristic that may influence the likelihood of an authentic leadership. Kernis and Goldman (2006) conceptualized dispositional authenticity as “the unobstructed operation of one’s core or true self in one’s daily enterprise” (p. 294). Thus, referring to self-consistency theory (Korman, 1970, 1976), It posit that dis- positional authenticity may influence the likelihood of leaders’ acting consistently with their values, beliefs, and strengths in adverse situations and persevering through challenges, which often result in them being perceived as authentic leaders. . It also contribute to the emerging theoretical and empirical research on authentic leadership by examining its potential influence on employee voice behavior promotive behavior that emphasizes expression of constructive challenge intended to improve rather than merely criticize (Van Dyne & LePine, 1998, p. 109). Moreover, It focuses on employee voice behaviour because previous studies have suggested that authentic leaders can, through balanced decision-making, transparency, and ethical role modeling, create conditions that motivate followers to display positive extra-role behaviour (Avolio, Gardner, Walumbwa, Luthans, & May 2004; Hsiung, 2012). In addition, employee voice behaviour is crucial for organizations because it promotes organizational effectiveness and prevents crises (Liang, Farh, & Farh, 2012).

The study makes a number of significant contributions. First, it advance authentic leadership theory by identifying potential determinants of authentic leadership. Specifically, It hypothesize that leader authentic personality can serve as a prerequisite to developing authentic leadership behavior. Organizations could benefit from a useful theoretical model of authentic leadership that clarifies how authentic leadership behavior manifests in organizations. Second, it contributes to the emerging theoretical and empirical studies on authentic leadership by analyzing followers’ OBSE as an explanatory mechanism through which authentic leaders can encourage their followers to engage in voice behaviour. By using this mediation model, rather than the leader-centered model that is used in most authentic leadership research, it provides a follower-centred model of the motivational mechanism that links authentic leadership to employee voice behaviour. Finally, as Gardner et al. (2005) suggested, authentic leadership theory has emphasized the developmental processes of authentic leadership and followership. It thus test a theoretical model involving the process of authentic leader and follower development. This approach clarifies the process of authentic leadership development.

Literature Review

Walumbwa et al. (2008) conceptualized authentic leadership and identified its four behavioural components: balanced processing, internalized moral perspective, relational transparency, and self-awareness. Balanced processing is the ability of leaders to resist denial, distortion, and exaggeration. Specifically, authentic leaders analyze all relevant information objectively before reaching a decision. Internalized moral perspective refers to how leader behaviours are guided by internal moral values and standards rather than by external pressure from sources such as peers and organizations. Relational transparency is leader behaviours aimed at enhancing trust through personal

disclosure such as openly sharing information and feelings with followers. Finally, self-awareness is the extent to which leaders understand their own motives, strengths, and weaknesses as well as recognize how followers view their leadership.

Leader's Authentic Personality and Authentic Leadership

Wood, Linley, Maltby, Baliousis, and Joseph (2008) presented a person-centered conception of authenticity, and highlighted three key components of dispositional authenticity: self alienation, authentic living, and accepting external influence. This construct assumes consistency among people's (1) primary experiences, (2) symbolized awareness, and (3) outward behaviour and communication (see Wood et al., 2008). The first component of authenticity is the extent to which an individual experiences self alienation according to conscious awareness and actual experience. Self-alienation refers to the lack of a sense of identity because of a subjective feeling of not knowing one's self (i.e., actual physiological states, emotions, and schematic beliefs). The second component of authenticity, authentic living, is the congruence between conscious awareness and outward behaviour; in short, it involves behaviour and expression that is consistent with one's own values, beliefs, and emotions. Accepting external influence is the final component of authenticity, and refers to the degree to which individuals accept the influence of other people; accepting external influence is the need to conform to the expectations of others.

Pinto, Maltby, Wood, and Day (2012) suggested that authentic living reflects feelings of authenticity, whereas self-alienation and accepting external influence represent inauthenticity. From a self-consistency perspective (Korman, 1976), people assimilate ideas that are consistent with their past experience and avoid ideas that are inconsistent with their past experience to maintain their self-concepts. On the basis of a previous analysis, it is argued that dispositional authenticity influences authentic behaviour by acting as a self-regulatory mechanism rooted in individuals' internalized inclination towards authenticity or inauthenticity, and therefore consider dispositional authenticity to be a critical antecedent of authentic leadership here.

Wood et al. (2008) maintained that people differ in the degree to which authenticity is central to their overall self-concepts, which implies that authenticity is more crucial for some people than it is for others. Accordingly, leaders whose authenticity has self-importance are motivated to act in ways that are consistent with common understandings of what it means to be an authentic person, and results in them being perceived as authentic leaders. The motivational power of being authentic mainly arises from individual desire for self-consistency (Korman, 1976; Wood et al., 2008). Leaders with dispositional authenticity must outwardly behave in a manner that is consistent with how they view themselves; they are also more likely to engage in authentic behaviours directed towards their followers. I thus propose that dispositional authenticity is positively related to authentic leadership because leaders that have dispositional authenticity are more likely to behave authentically, which manifests as authentic leadership.

Hypothesis 1. Leader Authentic Personality is Positively Related to Authentic Leadership.

Authentic Leadership and Employee Voice Behavior

Consistent with previous studies (Morrison, Wheeler-Smith, & Kamdar, 2010; Van Dyne & LePine, 1998), voice is defined as the discretionary communication of ideas, suggestions, concerns, or opinions intended to improve organizational or unit functioning. Walumbwa and Schaubroeck (2009) argued that voice involves the bottom-up process of rank-and-file employees catalyzing crucial changes and recommending improvements to standard procedures. Voice is typically characterized as a vital form of extra-role behaviour. However, unlike other cooperative forms of citizenship behaviours that are positive and discretionary, as well as those that promote effective organizational functioning (Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie, 2006), voice ideas that challenge current processes and decisions can generate negative interpersonal consequences for those who express them (Detert & Burris, 2007; Morrison & Milliken, 2000). Thus, employees often weigh the potential costs and benefits of a behaviour before expressing ideas. Detert and Burris (2007) indicated that employees' immediate work contexts (i.e., leader behaviour) strongly influences these calculations. It is anticipated that authentic leaders can encourage their followers to express their opinions. Previous theory building has stated that authentic leadership can foster employee voice behaviour (e.g., Hsiung, 2012). When authentic leaders display positive, transparent, honest, and ethical behaviours on the basis of their values and beliefs, their followers are likely to emulate them according to a role modeling process. Specifically, leaders perceived as authentic are crucial in fostering employee voice behaviour. Li et al. (2014) also argued that the self-disclosure of authentic leaders can build trusting relationships between leaders and followers. The trusting leader-follower relationship can encourage subordinates to favourably judge self-disclosure. Thus, these favourable perceptions may motivate subordinates to engage in voice behaviour. Supporting these arguments, Wong, Spence Laschinger, and Cummings (2010) studied 280 nurses and found that authentic leadership encourages follower voice behaviour. Recently, Hsiung (2012) studied 404 employees from a large real estate company in Taiwan and demonstrated that authentic leadership was substantially related to employee voice behaviour. Accordingly, hypothesized that authentic leadership can promote voice behaviour in work groups.

Hypothesis 2. Authentic Leadership is Positively related to Employee voice Behavior.

Mediating Role of OBSE

Studies on authentic leadership have primarily applied a leader centred perspective to explain how authentic leaders influence follower perceptions of leaders. For example, research has indicated that interpersonal justice (Li et al., 2014), leader-member exchange (LMX) (Hsiung, 2012; Wang et al., 2014), and identification with leaders (Wong et al., 2010) mediate the effect of authentic leadership on employee outcomes. By contrast, research on a follower-centred perspective, which highlights how leaders shape follower self-worth evaluations and subsequently their responses, is scant. However, numerous researchers have determined that leadership behaviour can influence followers' self-views (Bono & Judge, 2003; Farh & Chen, 2014; Shamir, House, & Arthur, 1993). Thus, a follower-centred approach is crucial to clarifying the salient influence of leadership behaviour on employee work outcomes because self-evaluation is a key motivational mechanism driving individual self-regulation, effort, and goal attainment (Bono & Judge, 2003; Shamir et al., 1993).

As applied to authentic leadership development in work groups, self-concept-based theory suggests that authentic leaders elevate member perceived self-worth or standing in such groups. Authentic leaders can thus increase employee OBSE, which is “the self-perceived value that individuals have of themselves as organizational members acting within an organizational context” (Pierce et al., 1989, p. 625). Specifically, employees with high OBSE perceive themselves as crucial and effective within organizations. In this study, the focus is on OBSE rather than on general self-esteem because, compared with general self-esteem, which reflects individuals' beliefs regarding their self-worth and competence, context-specific self-esteem (i.e., OBSE) is more effective in predicting work-related organizational phenomena (Pierce & Gardner, 2004; Pierce et al., 1989). According to self-concept-based theory (Shamir et al., 1993), self-esteem is based on “the sense of competence, power, achievement, or ability to cope with and control one's environment” (p. 580). When authentic leaders respect each of their followers, use follower input in making decisions, and understand followers' need to be valued, followers are more likely to feel crucial to their organizations. In other words, authentic leaders trust the ability of their followers. As stated, authentic leadership can increase follower self-worth. Research has also suggested that favourable leader treatment can heighten follower OBSE (Pierce et al., 1989). In this study, it is anticipated the effect of authentic leadership on follower OBSE to be heightened in a group context, where self-awareness is strengthened. Therefore, It is hypothesized that authentic leadership behaviour can foster follower self-esteem (i.e., OBSE).

Hypothesis 3. Authentic Leadership is Positively Related to OBSE.

It is further theorized that OBSE serves as a motivational mechanism that links authentic leadership to employee voice behaviour. OBSE represents a mediator of leader–follower relationships (e.g., Chan, Huang, Snape, & Lam, 2013; Farh & Chen, 2014). Thus, OBSE may link authentic leadership and voice behaviour. Followers with high OBSE tend to believe that they are valued members of organizations and have high social status among their co-workers. Therefore, they tend to believe that they have more opportunities to express themselves than their co-workers do (Liang et al., 2012). As discussed, followers of authentic leaders are particularly likely to have high OBSE levels. Such positive self-evaluations created by authentic leaders may motivate followers to engage with their work environment. Specifically, authentic leaders affect follower behaviour by influencing follower self-concept, which increases follower self-esteem and motivation. This proposed underlying mechanism is based on self-concept-based theory, which suggests that people tend to avoid dissonance and maintain balance or consistency in their images and actions. It is therefore hypothesized that authentic leadership strengthens subordinates' perceptions of OBSE, and this influence is realized through the perception of high value to the work group, and thereby making contributions to their workplace by speaking up their constructive ideas.

Hypothesis 4. OBSE Mediates the Relationship Between Authentic Leadership and Employee Voice Behavior.

Influence of Leader Authentic Personality on Employee Voice Behaviour

It is hypothesized that leader authentic personality is positively related to authentic leadership (i.e., Hypothesis 1) and that OBSE mediates the relationship between authentic leadership and voice behaviour (i.e., Hypothesis 4). To complete the proposed theoretical model, further examination of the indirect effect of leader authentic personality on voice behaviour. According to self-concept-based theory, the leader authentic personality–voice behaviour relationship might be more thoroughly explained by exploring the mediating roles of authentic leadership and employees' perceptions of OBSE. In other words, leader authentic personality may not be applicable as a sole predictor of follower voice behaviour. Instead, the manifestation of leader authenticity through authentic leader behaviour and simultaneously developing followers' positive self-development is likely to explain the relationship between leader authentic personality and follower voice behaviour. In particular, authentic leadership is characterized as a form of leadership style that originates from authentic functioning but, as a process of influence, is also aimed at the development of followers (Gardner et al., 2005; Leroy et al., 2015). Accordingly, It is argued that leader authentic personality is related to employee behaviour only through its influence on leader behaviour and thus on follower positive self-development. Therefore, I propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5. Leader Authentic Personality Is Indirectly Related To Employee Voice Behaviour Through The Mediating Influence Of Authentic Leadership And Thus Employee Obse

Theoretical Framework

Methods and Analysis

Data for this study were collected from subordinates and their immediate supervisors from different functional work groups in a large public healthcare organization. The access to the participating organization was obtained through personal networks. These work groups are responsible for various organizational operations, such as Human Resources, administration, finance, accounting, Quality Assurance, and Research & Development. Participation was voluntary, and the confidentiality of participants was assured during the survey distribution and collection. The surveys were collected during working hours. Direct reports reported on their own OBSE and their supervisors' authentic leadership, whereas supervisors reported on their own authentic personalities and their subordinates' voice behaviours

The survey respondents consisted of 200 subordinates and 20 supervisors; yielding response rates of 83.1% and 100%, respectively. Among the group members, 77% were male, the average age was 30.06 years (standard deviation [SD] = 3.17), the average group tenure was 18.64 months (SD = 5.15), the average tenure with the immediate supervisor was 12.19 months (SD = 5.68), and all group members had undergraduate or

higher degrees. Of the group leaders, 92% were male, the average age was 38.92 years (SD = 2.67), and all group leaders had undergraduate or higher degrees.

Organization-Based Self-Esteem

Subordinate OBSE was measured using a 10-item OBSE scale developed and validated by Pierce et al. (1989). Subordinates were instructed to respond to what extent they agreed with statements such as “I am valuable around my workplace” and “I am helpful around here”. The Cronbach’s alpha (α) coefficient for this scale was .90.

Voice Behaviour

Supervisors rated their individual members’ voice behaviour by using Van Dyne and LePine’s (1998) 6-item scale. Sample items included “[This employee] suggests ideas for new projects or changes in procedure” and “develops and makes recommendations concerning problems that affect this work group”. The Cronbach’s α coefficient for this scale was .86.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 1. Results of the confirmatory factor analyses.

Measurement models	χ^2	df	$\Delta\chi^2$	RMSEA	SRMR	CFI	TLI
Four-factor model (baseline model)							
AP, AL, OBSE, and voice behaviour	1,079.95**	896		.05	.05	.90	.89
Three-factor model							
Combine AP and AL into one construct	3,085.48**	899	1,505.53**	.08	.09	.74	.72
Three-factor model							
Combine AL and OBSE into one construct	3,555.57**	899	1,975.62**	.09	.11	.68	.66
Two-factor model							
Combine AP, AL, and OBSE into one construct	4,874.17**	901	3,294.22**	.10	.14	.52	.50
One-factor model							
Combine all four factors into one construct	5,741.13**	902	4,161.18**	.12	.14	.42	.39

AP: leader authentic personality; AL: authentic leadership; OBSE: organization-based self-esteem; The χ^2 difference was compared with the value of the four-factor model (baseline model).

**p < .01 (two-tailed tests).

Table 2 shows the correlations and descriptive statistics for all study variables. Hypothesis 1 suggested a positive relationship between leader authentic personality and authentic leadership. Because these variables are at the same level (i.e., the group level), hierarchical regression analyses was conducted.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics, reliabilities, and correlations among study variables.

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1. Sex of supervisor ^a	.92	.27															
2. Education of supervisor ^b	2.84	.36	-.04														
3. Age of supervisor	38.92	2.67	.16*	.02													
4. Sex of subordinate ^a	.77	.43	.02	-.06	-.07												
5. Education of subordinate ^b	2.50	.50	.07	-.03	.01	-.10*											
6. Age of subordinate	30.06	3.17	.09	.11*	-.01	-.02	.54**										
7. Work group tenure (months)	18.64	5.15	.09	.03	.03	-.02	.23**	.17**									
8. Dyadic length (months)	12.19	5.68	.03	.02	-.05	-.01	.11**	.09	.31**								
9. Group size	4.92	1.41	.01	.11*	.16**	-.04	-.07	.01	.13**	-.04							
10. Psychological safety	3.34	.89	.03	-.08	.03	.04	.03	-.07	.03	.05	.01	(.89)					
11. Leader-member exchange	3.23	.60	-.13**	-.05	-.04	-.06	.02	-.05	.00	.04	-.26**	.07	(.83)				
12. Authentic personality	4.32	.67	.10	.08	.10	.00	.05	-.04	-.01	.05	-.30**	.03	.08	(.89)			
13. Authentic leadership	3.35	.78	.00	-.02	-.03	.05	.03	-.01	-.04	.18**	-.32**	.02	.28**	.36**	(.93)		
14. OBSE	3.50	.73	.03	-.02	-.10	.00	.10	.01	.14**	.50**	-.14**	.10*	.07	.12*	.19**	(.90)	
15. Voice behaviour	2.90	.92	-.04	-.05	-.12*	-.06	.21**	.04	.12*	.25**	-.22**	.25**	.20**	.17**	.25**	.40**	(.86)

n = 408; Coefficient α reliabilities are reported in parentheses on the diagonal; OBSE = organization-based self-esteem.

*p < .05, **p < .01 (two-tailed tests).

^aSex: 0 = female, 1 = male.

^bEducation: 1 = high school, 2 = college degree, 3 = graduate degree.

Table 3. Hierarchical Regression Results for H1

Table # 4 Hierarchical Linear

Modeling for H2-5

Variables	β	t	Model	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Sex of supervisor	-.07	-.77	Variables	1				
Education of supervisor	-.12	-1.30	Intercept	3.17***	2.88***	2.64***	2.74***	2.74***
Age of supervisor	-.04	-.47	Level 1 variables					
ΔR^2	.06		Sex of subordinate	.00	-.10	-.10	-.10	-.10
Authentic personality	.485	.96**	Education of subordinate	.09	.31***	.30***	.28***	.28***
ΔR^2	.49**		Age of subordinate	-.01	-.02	-.01	-.01	-.01
R^2 for total equation	.55		Work group tenure of subordinate	.01	.02*	.02*	.02*	.02*
n = 90 work groups; standardized coefficients are reported for the final step in each model.				subordinate				
			Dyadic length	.06***	.03***	.02***	.01	.01
** p < .01 (two-tailed tests).			Psychological safety	.06*	.23***	.24***	.22***	.22***
Leader-member exchange	-.02	.15***		.12**	.13**	.13*		

Discussion

A recent review of studies on authentic leadership highlighted the necessity of investigating the antecedents and consequences of authentic leadership (Gardner et al., 2011). Therefore, in the present study, I developed and tested a multilevel model of the antecedents and consequences of authentic leadership. I reached three main conclusions. First, guided by self-consistency theory (Korman, 1970, 1976), I observed that leader authentic personality was positively related to subordinate perceptions of authentic leadership. Second, on the basis of self-concept-based theory, I determined that OBSE is a catalyst in the relationship between authentic leadership and employee voice behaviour. Third, I hypothesized that leader authentic personality is indirectly associated with employee voice behaviour through the mediating mechanisms of authentic leadership and thus subordinate OBSE. The theoretical and practical implications of this study's findings and limitations are presented as follows.

Conclusion

To establish enduring organizations and create long-term value for shareholders, modern organizations should value authentic leadership development strategies. According to self-consistency and self-concept-based theories, I developed a multilevel mediation model of authentic leadership development. The findings indicate that leader authentic personality is a crucial predictor of authentic leadership. Furthermore, leader authentic personality may influence employee voice behaviour through the mediating mechanisms of authentic leadership and subordinate OBSE. The current study has major implications for organizations and managers because it clarifies how authentic leadership emerges in organizations and the effectiveness of authentic leadership development. Thus, this study can serve as a springboard for future investigations into other constructs and the underlying processes that facilitate authentic leadership development.

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